

STRUCTURE OF A SAMPLE TRAINING COURSE AND MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR IT

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Annotation:

the structure of training, elements of training, type of training, type of training, teaching methodology, modern requirements for training are mentioned.

Keywords: educational process, lesson training, structure of educational training , training elements, training type, training types, modern requirements.

Introduction

Educational training is a complex form of organizing the educational process, which requires a great responsibility from the pedagogue in the process of conducting the training, a creative approach to its planning. In this case, it is important to divide the time correctly, control each part of training in the work of students, and personal training activities.

Combined training includes the following steps:

- ✓ organizational;
- ✓ homework check button;
- ✓ comprehensive examination of knowledge;
- ✓ actualization of knowledge;
- ✓ new knowledge acquisition and knowledge consolidation training;
- ✓ homework instruction;
- ✓ end of training session, reflection session.

Organizational stage: very short-term, determines all the psychological mood of the training. Warming, sweet words of the pedagogue, calm, trusting habits are required for the fulfillment of these tasks. The ability of learners to activate the object experience ensures their motivation and engagement in collaborative activities. It is not enough to update the knowledge and skills that are sometimes limited in this field. A person consciously acquires only the knowledge that is acquired by the personal content.

Homework is given in almost every class, but sometimes this assignment is limited to information about what to do. However, there must be information about its implementation. This does not mean that the pedagogue should dictate the procedure for doing homework. There should be a plan for its implementation together with learners, and necessary explanations. Lack of this skill leads to homework problems, lack of knowledge, and learning problems. Sometimes, due to lack of time and proper planning of training, the last two steps are left out: conclusion and reflection. But they also have important psychological significance. Evaluating the results of the learner serves as a stimulus for further work, for proving achievements, and for creating a positive emotional mood. Reflection also allows to develop the emotional range of learners, to master the principles of cooperation.

The structure of the training session and the method of conducting it depend on the didactic goals and tasks that are solved in the process of education and training. Depending on the most common methods and sources of teaching, one or another type of training can have several types. The structure of the training session is the summation of the elements of the training session, which ensure the integrity and completeness of the training session in various options.

Exemplary structural elements of training

No	Training organization	Time (minutes)	Work to be done in training
1.	Organizing the beginning of the training.	2	To attract the attention of the learners to the educational activity, to interest them, to announce the topic to them and to tell them about it.
2.	Homework check.	3	Determining the level of mastery of the previous subject's educational material. Preparing students to receive new information.
3.	I love you.	20	Learning new material. Presentation of scientific, interesting new materials with the involvement of learners themselves.
4.	Advance consolidation of knowledge.	5	After explaining the new material, using maxcuc tasks aimed at applying knowledge and developing skills.
5.	Independent work of learners with subsequent supervision.	10	Monitoring and evaluation of independent work.
6.	End of training.	2	Determining what students have learned in the training, what new and useful things they have

			learned for themselves, and how to evaluate knowledge.
7.	Information about the housekeeper.	2	Declaring homework and explaining how to do it.

The organization of the educational process imposes a number of requirements on its participants: clearly and creatively fulfilling the technical-methodical requirements for the training, accurately determining the type of training, its place in the training department, the inter-training communication system, the effectiveness of each training; taking into account specific educational opportunities of learners, the level of upbringing, the level of formation of the group community, their interests, aspirations, needs, and the necessary orientation to eliminate knowledge gaps; thinking and solving educational tasks together (formation of knowledge, skills, abilities, cognitive abilities, readiness for independent education), education (worldview, active life position, correct discipline and communication experience, formation of personal qualities, self-education and mental development), intelligence , development of attention, reception, memory, thinking, thinking, speech, freedom, separation of the most pressing tasks of training, taking into account the team's capabilities and capabilities, clarifying them; choosing the structure of training and the pace of conducting it, which ensures the successful solution of the assigned tasks and the careful use of training time; to ensure the attention of students to important scientific concepts, theoretical procedures, laws, worldview, educational ideas of educational material, to distinguish between lessons in the content of teaching, to ensure the close connection of the training content with life, with the needs of society, with the personal life experiences and interests of students; to ensure the practical, goal-oriented nature of the educational process, the creation of clear opportunities for students to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities; active methods, intensive teaching, use of oral, demonstrative and practical, reproductive and problem-research methods of teaching in classes, methods of independent work of learners and work under the guidance of a pedagogue, methods of arousing interest in knowledge in learners, respect for understanding, duty, responsibility and discipline methods; conducting frontal forms of work in a group and individually, striving to organize educational work in the same way as collective activity; differentiated approach to learners; formation of conscious and active attitude of all learners to their educational activities, skills of organizing academic work in training, use of educational and developmental opportunities in training, control and evaluation of their knowledge, skills and qualifications; to be respectful of the recipient; development of the cabinet system of teaching in accordance with the requirements of scientific and technical progress, comprehensive use of various educational resources (textbooks, manuals, information resources); to follow acceptable hygienic and ecstatic conditions for working in training; determining the content and size of homework taking into account the time, not allowing students to get tired, and if necessary, explaining how to do homework; making a plan of training, ensuring its progress depending on the change of educational situations, and determining the results of education, upbringing, and development of learners based on the results of the analysis obtained during the training, comparing them with the tasks of the pedagogue, identifying achievements and shortcomings, taking into account the results of this analysis when planning the next training.

Didactic requirements: implementation of basic didactic principles in training: scientificity, systematicity, sequence, understanding, activity, unity of education and upbringing, connection of

theory and practice, demonstrability, solidity of knowledge, knowledge of individual approach to students, etc.; correctly determine the purpose of the training, its exact place in the general training system; to determine the optimal content of training goals and requirements of science; educational, training and development purposes; the pedagogue's high teaching skills, creative use of teaching methods and methods, the ability to master modern didactic techniques; ensuring high cognitive activity, independent learning of the material, solving problematic tasks, performing tasks of a creative nature; interaction of frontal, group and individual work in training; wide use of didactic materials of different levels of complexity, stratified approach to students who are not ready to learn the learning material; changing the types of activities of learners in training; consistency in teaching (making interdisciplinary communication for the purpose of forming the system of knowledge, skills and scientific worldview, ensuring the connection of these trainings with the previous ones); the content, volume and structure of the educational material, activation of formation of basic knowledge, skills and qualifications of learners; describe new material; consolidation of material; teaching: universality, problematic, individual and differentiated approach, demonstrativeness, use of technical means of teaching, interdisciplinary communication; teaching: working on the personal development of the learner, activity, independence, creativity, research, general educational skills, academic competences; use of objective methods of control, comprehensive evaluation of the knowledge and skills of learners; control and assessment: checking homework, current feedback, assessment of educational achievements of learners, the level of formation of educational skills and competencies, and educational-cognitive competencies.

Organizational requirements: preparation of a classroom, a workplace for training; accuracy, careful use of time in training; creating a business environment; discipline of learners; the purpose of the training is the content of training, structure of methods, efficient use of time. The thought-out structure of the training session differs as follows: proper organization, efficient use of time, clearly setting the learning goal, forming the thematic and specific tasks of the training session, the correct structure of the purpose, content and methods of conducting the training session, using teaching instruments depending on the situations in the training session. , mobile and technologies) use.

Educational requirements: setting educational tasks of training, providing moral and ideological direction; implementation of educational opportunities in which the content and methods of teaching are established; influencing the motivational framework of the learner, forming a positive attitude towards education, developing their independent creative abilities; to adhere to the tact of teaching, to establish high demands of the pedagogue together with respect for the individuality of the learner.

Psychological requirements: training is aimed at developing knowledge of psychological processes: attention, imagination, memory, thinking, thinking, etc.; recording the mental state and psychological abilities of students during training; to be able to organize the attention of learners, to take into account their age and individual abilities, to create a positive emotional environment during training; behavior of the pedagogue, his ability to attract learners, self-control, kindness, correctness; readiness and attentiveness of the pedagogue, regular self-control, optimism, freshness, ability to control one's mood; demandingness, respect, truthfulness, respect for the individual of the learner, adherence to the tact of teaching; designing the personal development of each learner within the limits of learning each educational activity and educational subjects; use of methodological tools, psychological-educational means of providing personal development.

Hygienic requirements: warning against mental and physical exhaustion; temperature mode; room lighting; the height of the furniture for the learner; proper placement of learners; prevention of mental and social exhaustion of learners; compliance of students with the norms of using computer equipment; Timely and quality physical education.

Technical requirements: the optimal pace and rhythm of training; completion of each step; emotionality of training; cooperation, creative labor activity atmosphere; changing types of activities; speech proficiency of all participants of the educational process.

Basic requirements for training management: organizational level: duty gives an account; learning and control of students' knowledge: use of various forms such as oral, written, frontal, combined, test on the subject; conveying to them the purpose of the training, every step of it: expressing the topic and purpose of the training; separation of key questions in the presentation of the original material, careful distribution of information; the culture of providing new material: accuracy, logicity, fluency of speech, scientificity of presentation; appropriate selection of teaching materials and teaching methods for each lesson, taking into account the readiness of learners: compliance of the material with modern normative documents; consolidation of new material; the accuracy of the housekeeper; dependence of educational and educational tasks; connection of teaching and upbringing with life, creation of conditions for special self-expression and affirmation of the individual in training, and creation of an atmosphere of creative, active work and curiosity in training.

Training development. When preparing for the training, the pedagogue should determine its purpose, training content, teaching methods, training structure. The purpose of the training is to achieve the results of the pedagogue's cooperation with them in teaching, educating and developing students. They can be educational, educational and developmental. They are closely related. Depending on specific circumstances, their role in organizing and conducting training is different. Every training should be developmental. Learning should bring a sense of satisfaction, joy, and new strength to the incon. Therefore, the time of training is limited, it should be used wisely. This can be achieved by the preparation of pedagogues and students, the availability of subjects, the equipment of training sessions, and the achievement of results.

Completion is one of the requirements for training. Educational activity is a coherent, logically completed part of the educational environment, limited to a specific time frame, in which all relevant elements of the educational process (content, objects, methods, organizational minutes) are shown. The result depends on their thoughtful, interactive and camera use.

It is known that the system of educational training for any academic subject has periodicity in the didactic sense. Usually, the period is related to the significant unity of the educational material, the topic and has the following didactic values: learning new material, consolidation, repetition of the learned, control of knowledge, application of knowledge to solve tasks, formation of practical skills and competencies, personal and social competences.

Specific requirements: the pedagogue should have mastered the subject of education, teaching methods, and the training should be educational and developing; development work should be carried out in each training, the material presented should be scientific, reliable, understandable, connected with life and based on the previous experience of the learners; an individualized approach to learners and interdisciplinary communication should be implemented in each training session; the training should be equipped (with technical facilities of teaching, didactic materials (table, map, illustration, tect, diagram, discussion algorithm, program, etc.); all the material is

connected with the logic of the training and should be able to the level of development of the learner and innovative processes in the training should be implemented; it is important to introduce computer training; a protective regimen should be strictly observed during the training: conducting a physical session (2-3 minutes), appropriateness of furniture for the age of the student, appropriateness of didactic materials in terms of size and color, appropriateness of the educational loader for the age of the student, canitar- compliance with hygienic requirements, the training should help to solve the urgent tasks facing the educational student: the pedagogue should support the learner who acquires the pact in every way, help the learner with anomalous development in social adaptation.

When preparing for the training, the following should be kept in mind: training topic. type of training, training goals, tasks, performance of all aspects of training to achieve training goals, forms and methods of training, evaluation of learners, analysis of training. The availability of one or another part of the training depends on the type of training.

Teaching methods: explanation, story, demonstration, observation, work on the book, game, exercise, practical-laboratory work, practical work, independent work, application of technical means of teaching, computerized and problem teaching.

Ucul is a part of the method. For example, when using the exercise method, the following methods are used: reporting on the condition of the task, writing the conditions, performing the tasks, analyzing the results of the completed tasks, monitoring the correct completion of the tasks.

Sample training plan: training type: combined, training thematic, training tasks. Training equipment.

1. Organizational issue. Purpose: training students for training work. The content of the lesson: finding one's place when the bell rings, greeting each other, calculating the duty, identifying absentees, writing a letter, organizing students' mood and attention to work, telling the topic and purpose of the training.

2. Check homework. Purpose: to check that the homework is done correctly, to identify typical errors, to determine the level of knowledge of students, to repeat the material, to eliminate identified gaps in knowledge during the examination.

Possible variants of homework examination: frontal and docked individual examination, frontal written examination (in front of the desk according to cards), individual written examination, full examination (frontal and individual, written and oral), practical work, computer control, examination of notebooks, teaching technical vocitas.

3. Preparing students to learn new material. Purpose: organization of cognitive activity of learners. To inform about the topic, purpose and tasks of the new material to be studied. To demonstrate the practical importance of learning new material, to realize interest and attention to learning a new topic. A new concept can be introduced in different ways: riddle, rebuc, crossword, fourth plus game, vocabulary work (related to new material), problem question.

4. Notification of new material. Purpose: to give clear descriptions of the task, rules, and conditions to be studied. It is possible to report on new material : in the form of a teacher's narrator (scientific, universal, emotional, sequential, demonstrative, with vocabulary work, with summaries); independent familiarization with new material, with ways of observing and using textbooks; introductory speech (if the learner has information on this topic); exchange of conversation and story; application of teaching techniques.

5. Consolidation of acquired knowledge. Purpose: to consolidate the necessary knowledge and skills for the independent work of learners on new material, to teach them to apply knowledge in similar situations. Used methods: conversation, working with textbooks, working with notebooks, practical work, computerized tasks, didactic games, technical means of teaching, tables, charts and texts, independent work.

6. Termination. Purpose: to conclude and make conclusions about how the group worked in the training, to record the work of the learners, to determine what new things they learned in the training: summaries, to understand the learned material, to write homework, to evaluate the work of the learners.

Indicators of degree of familiarity include: degree of differentiation or familiarity. It characterizes the most compact level of learning. The learner differentiates objects, processes, and events from their counterparts when they are given these ready-made. Cannot write, explain, solve, apply in practice. Gives answers to questions of the same complexity, attempts to find the correct answer are observed; get tired Learners can tell the content of the subject, rules, etc. from a deep understanding. They respond only to questions in the reproductive plan, sometimes in a specific sequence; to understand Learners not only describe, but also explain, give examples, understand the essence of words; application (reproductive level). The learner can apply theoretical knowledge in simple tasks. Normal skills can be converted to normal skills during their application; transfer The learner knows how to creatively apply the acquired theoretical knowledge in a new noctandart situation.

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